

The Relation between the Surface Tension and Viscosity of Liquids.

Part I.

By

RAM KRISHEN SHARMA.

Porter (*Phil. Mag.*, 23, 458) finds that if the viscosities of two liquids be determined over a very large range of temperature, certain temperatures can be found at which their viscosities are the same and if a curve be plotted with T and T/T_0 , where T and T_0 are the absolute temperatures at which their viscosities are the same, a straight line is obtained.

Similarly, if we determine the surface tension of two liquids over a very large range of temperature, certain temperatures can be found at which their surface tensions are the same and if a curve be plotted with T and T/T_0 , a straight line is obtained. As an example we take chlorobenzene and diethyl ether:—

No.	Temperature of chlorobenzene	Temperature of ether	Surface tension.	T/T_0 .
1.	150°	66°	17.67	1.2471
2.	200°	101°	12.72	1.2641
3.	250°	147°	8.04	1.266
4.	300°	180°	3.79	1.264

An attempt has been made to find a relationship between surface tension and viscosity. Water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, benzene and acetic acid have been considered. The values for surface tension and viscosity have been taken from the tables of Landolt and Börnstein.

It is found that if the logarithm of viscosity be plotted against the logarithm of surface tension, a straight line is

obtained, and the following general equation is applicable to ethyl and methyl alcohols, benzene and acetic acid.

$$\log \lambda = M \log \mu + C$$

where λ represents surface tension; M is the slope which the straight line makes with the positive direction of the x axis; μ represents viscosity; C is the intercept which the straight line makes with the y axis.

The equation fairly holds good for water also.

Ethyl Alcohol.

No.	Temperature	Viscosity	Surface tension	
			Observed	Calculated
1.	10°	0·01450	23·95	23·95
2.	20°	0·01190	22·03	22·11
3.	30°	0·00989	21·13	21·52
4.	40°	0·00827	20·20	20·03
5.	50°	0·00697	19·25	19·13
6.	60°	0·00591	18·43	18·29
7.	70°	0·00501	17·53	17·53

Calculated from $\log \lambda = 0·2718 \log \mu + 0·5102$.

Summary.

1. If the surface tensions of two liquids be determined over a large range of temperature, certain temperatures can be found at which their surface tensions are the same, and if a curve be plotted representing the ratios of their absolute temperature against the absolute temperatures of the others, a straight line is obtained.

2. When the logarithm of surface tension is plotted against the logarithm of viscosity a straight line is obtained.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
FORMAN CHRISTIAN COLLEGE,
LAHORE.

Received, August 13, 1925.